

Supplementary figures S2 for “Context-dependent effects of glucocorticoids on the lizard gut microbiome”, MacLeod KJ, Kohl KD, Trevelline BK, Langkilde T. (Molecular Ecology 2021)

Supp Fig S2a. Number of treatments received by control (blue filled circles) and CORT-treated (red filled squares) females at three stages of gestation (non-gravid, mid-gestation, late-gestation). Lines represent mean \pm standard error.

Supp Fig 2b. There was a significant interaction between gestation bin and CORT treatment on the number of observed ASVs and Faith's phylogenetic diversity. Post-hoc analyses show that the number of ASVs hosted by CORT-treated individuals was significantly higher than in untreated individuals in late gestation (denoted with *).

Supp Fig S2c. Community membership (left panel) and structure (right panel) of females treated with CORT (shades of red) or a control control (shades of blue). These figures show the individual points of those represented in Figure 2 of the main text.

Supp Fig S2d. Relative abundance (%) of (A) *Erysipelatoclostridium*; (B) *Catabacter*; (C) *Butyricimonas*; (D) *Bilophila*; and (E) *Anaerofustis* in the gut microbiota of control (control) females (blue filled circles) and CORT-treated (red filled squares) females at three stages of gestation (non-gravid, mid-gestation, late-gestation). Points represent individual values.